

Interview transcript STE *Information feedbacks and lobbying*

Interview date: 18.04.2023

Participants: P5, P6

P5 [00:00:02] I can do that after a few once.

I [00:00:04] Yeah. Perfect. Thank you very much. And yeah, regarding the time, so P6 already said that she might, she needs to leave a little early. So at 5:30. So my idea is that we have, like 15 minutes now for our introduction and explanation of objectives and methodology and then about an hour for the real interview. And then we see how much time is left for a bit reflection and feedback, but we can see that later. So yeah, maybe I quickly introduce myself. So I'm I [Interviewer]. I'm Master student at the University of Osnabrück, and my program is called Environmental Systems and Resource Management, and I'm currently writing my master's thesis in collaboration with the Potsdam Institute of Climate Impact Research. That's how I got in touch with you. And as you already know, my thesis is about social tipping elements for transitioning to regenerative agriculture and maybe a personal link to agriculture. So I was always interested in social processes and environmental processes. So agriculture kind of combines both for me and also regenerative agriculture represents for me at least, like a solution for many problems that we're currently facing, like climate change and also biodiversity issues and things like this. So that's how I ended here. And yeah, now it would be great if you could also introduce yourself maybe quickly with your name, your background, and also your relation to regenerative agriculture. I don't know who wants to start?

P5 [00:01:54] Yeah. Okay. Yeah. Okay. I'm P5, and I'm photographer and storyteller. And since five years, I'm very much involved. Or I'm sort of focusing on regenerative pioneers who are farmers, mostly who are starting up their regenerative farm or who are planning to start one or who are already there for a couple of years. And I want to find out what is motivating them to do this and just hear their story and feature it to inspire others to maybe do the same. I'm involved with the ORGANISATION as their photographer, a storyteller. So I've been visiting many farms in the Netherlands at this last summer where I was also in Spain and Italy and France to see what's what's going on there on different regenerative projects.

P6 [00:03:28] I answer than. I am not like in this specific type of regenerative agriculture, but I am working in an area development company. So it is becoming more and more part of our work gladly. So I've done a course last year at Bodemzicht, and what it takes for me to do the even setting up everything for a regenerative farm. And yeah, I've been ready to use a lot in my projects as well. How can we do this from bottom literally and so the greens and blues, how can those be vital and yeah, how can we try these more? Although we also have to build dwellings. So there was a bit of a

search. I've done a lot of, the last couple of years, of visiting eco villages in Europe and to see how they do it combined with the living as well. And that's something for me that's related. Yeah, and maybe it's next step. I'm curious to see how we can get this more into area development as well.

I [00:05:02] Sounds good. Thank you. And so now I would quickly explain the objectives of the interview and also the methodology I would like to follow. So I am not sure if you remember, but in the workshops last year, we looked at a lot of interventions and tipping dynamics in different areas of the land use system. So we had education, law and policy, finance and so on. And so today we look at information feedbacks, lobbying and inspiring, and then we combine three of these areas. And since we're quite similar from what were mentioned last year, and also because I don't have the capacity to do all the interviews. So we had to combine some of the elements and we chose to do that for these three. And so for me, this social tipping element, so information feedback, lobbying and inspiring and is really about information and knowledge dissemination and to raise awareness. So to get more farmers to see regenerative agriculture, but also more people and the public in general. And for me, this social tipping element also encompasses research as part of this knowledge dissemination. And so I hope this works for you as well. Yeah. And the goal for this interview is really to find out how exactly the interventions that were mentioned last year contribute to transition to regenerative agriculture. So we want to focus on interconnections and how these interventions really can help to transition. And I would just read out a definition of regenerative agriculture. I know there is a lot of debate around what regenerative agriculture is. And if you object or if you have really huge objections, we can discuss it. But I would like to leave it like it is and continue. So I take or I took the definition from Schrefel et al, and they defined regenerative agriculture as an approach to farming that uses soil conservation as the entry point to regenerate and contribute to multiple provisioning, regulating and supporting ecosystem services with the objectives that this would enhance not only the environmental but also the social and economic dimensions of sustainable food production. So I hope.

P6 [00:07:43] You put that in the chat? I think there were a lot of words.

I [00:07:49] Yeah, sure. That's a good idea.

P5 [00:07:58] Good idea. Yeah.

I [00:08:01] Can you read it?

P5 [00:08:03] Thank you. Yeah.

I [00:08:13] And so the output of this interview will be a map or a diagram, um, which will help me in the end to see effects of different interventions on the transition to regenerative agriculture. And my plan is also to combine the diagrams of different areas. So for example, to combine education with law and policy or information feedback with finance. Yeah. So now we will go directly into the board. So I will share my screen. So and it might be a little bit small at the beginning. So I think the best thing is to do it on full screen and just leave the microphone on. So I think it's the most easy thing to see. Is it readable? More or less.

P5 [00:09:22] Yeah. So, yeah, some of it.

I [00:09:32] Okay. And so quickly to the set up. So I decided to put the elements that were mentioned in three different categories. So there are interventions. So this is really a collection of elements that were mentioned in the workshops last year. And why there are some green? Yeah, I would come to that later. And the other category are conditions. And these conditions are also extracted from the workshop results, but also from literature. And these are really elements that enable social tipping or the transition to happen. And the difference between conditions and interventions is sorry. Um, yeah. So the difference between the two is that, like the conditions are really elements that need to be fulfilled so that the transitioning process can happen. For example, public knowledge needs to rise. Otherwise, the transition won't happen. And interventions are elements that can trigger processes that lead to the fulfilment of these conditions. So, for example, information campaigns. So information campaigns can lead to the increase of public knowledge. Is this clear?

P6 [00:11:03] May I ask you question like more of was there, who are focussed on sort of social tipping point and after the transition? Is it like a broad audience or is it farmers or what, what's your audience?

I [00:11:18] I think it's a broad audience. I mean, in the end, the farmers needs to implement practices to transition to regenerative agriculture. So you could say that the goal is to get more farmers to implement practices. But of course there are also other stakeholders which are important. And I guess I mean, that's from what I know so far. Does it answer your question?

P6 [00:11:47] Yeah, kind of. Because I was looking at you post-its and I was like, Hmm. these are really these are really broad things you are addressing, so. Okay. Yeah, that was something, I was thinking.

I [00:12:03] Um. No. Yeah, you're right. They're quite broad. And. Yeah, so I really I retrieved them from the workshops last year, and I also condensed them a little bit because, like, there are much more posted and I tried to reduce them a little bit, Um, but there is a third category which are

consequences, and this is kind of a free space for possible elements that results when a condition is met. Um, and might also be that there are consequences for other areas. So I listed them here and for the interview now, we will go through these three categories step by step. Um, but we will also look at all of them together, and as we collected a lot of elements during the workshop last year, I really would like you to focus on the interconnections between all these elements. Um, so it would be great if we could identify links between these three categories, but also, um, within these categories, for example, how it already happened here in the conditions. Um, and to sign these or to note these interconnections. Um, I would like to follow like a certain guideline kind of, um, so an arrow always shows an influence from one element to another and we have two kinds of arrows. So there are positive and negative arrows. And the positive arrow shows that, um, the two elements change in the same direction. So if A increases also B increases, and if A decreases also B decreases. And a negative arrow says that these two elements change in opposite direction. So if A increases B decreases and if A decreases B increases. So if we look at an example, um, so if public knowledge, for example increases, we could assume that also more people would recognise values for nature, agriculture and food. So there is a positive arrow. And the idea is really that you kind of discuss with each other and that we brainstorm together and I will try to draw the map and kind of put the post-its together how you say it. And then we try to build a map together. That's this idea. So are there any questions regarding these instructions? Or is it clear?

P5 [00:14:49] So basically this is like this. All these themes are what we are going to discuss and see how they influence each other, if it's either a positive or a negative, and then also in between interventions and the conditions.

I [00:15:23] Exactly. It's also possible to add elements. Or if you think there is something missing. Yeah. Sorry, I forgot to say. But. Yeah. If you think there is something important missing, you can add. It's more like. So these elements that are already there is kind of an inspiration. So to start with something and not to start from scratch. Um, but you can also say, okay, this intervention is really not important at all and we can just delete it from there. Yeah, so that's also possible, but you don't have to. I mean, yeah, it's really also an experiment, kind of what would come out of it.

P6 [00:16:06] So we are to focus on the interrelations also between all the things, but for me. I'm a system nerd. It lacks a bit of structure for me. Like you have all of these kind of dimensions that are interrelated and there's no priority in these post-its yet. Do you want us to prioritise or because that's also something that. I see a lot of things. They all have to be related to each other. I don't see how we can do this. So the things that I use for, like in the Netherlands we also have a lot of participation. I'm not sure if that's the word in English. But it's all about collaboration and co-creating, and those those kind of things which have four main categories, how you can categorise all those different audiences and market place and institutions and schools. It's market. It's the government and it's the

civilisation. And it's just people and those four are interrelated. That's if the people don't want to implement the things that the government is saying, this kind of thing. So that helps to understand which post-it is in which category for me that helps. I'm not sure how Gabriela feels about this. There's something I see now like it's about farmers. It's about public knowledge, it's about networks. It's a lot of different things. For me, it helps to get an overall view of how we can define those different audiences.

I [00:18:04] We could do that. I mean, if it helps you, we can just shift around the post-its that's a bit and do like a little like kind of clusters or areas. That's what you mean right? To to bring this a little bit in a system. Am Should I give you maybe a few minutes to read through the post-its. And then we start with the prioritisation and clustering so you can take some time to read through all of them to get familiar with them. Would this be helpful?

P6 [00:18:44] Yeah. Could be.

I [00:18:45] Then I just like give you maybe 2 minutes to read through them. And I leave you a little bit.

I [00:21:11] So how is it going? I mean. Are you good to continue or do you need more time?

P5 [00:21:20] Good.

I [00:21:26] Okay. Are there any question in terms of terminology, so are there any terms not clear

I [00:21:47] And so for structuring it a little bit. So, P6, you've suggested to have like and to to make a structure regarding how you all these areas like people that are concerned in a way. Is that true? So we have like the public and the farmers and maybe more like institutions such as politics or schools or how would cluster it.

P6 [00:22:21] Yeah. I was trying to find this image I was looking for. Of course, I don't work on your moral board. You have to put it in, but that's the link. It's a triangle, actually, if this is. Institutions like universities and schools, but it helps to structure. I have posted in a chat. I'm trying to find the right one. Mm hmm. It's Dutch though, but we will translate it for you. The people are in the left corner, and the market is right corner and the government is in the top corner. We have different kind of formal, informal lines. You have public and private separations and nonprofits profits. And this is about the change in positions of what's happening nowadays, that the inhabitants, the people are more involved in decision making and getting more plans into things like that. So maybe we can start with it. Maybe it doesn't work, but we can try to give it a go. And then we can see what's happening

on local. Um, sorry I'm mixing with words. Level. Yeah, local level, regional level and landscape or land level. You also have, like, a different position in the rest of the farm. Or you can do a little other things local, but you can also contribute on a like land scale or something.

I [00:24:30] Okay. So. So how would you know if you say, okay. I mean, I think it's hard to put the triangle in here now, but maybe if you could say, okay, local is more like on the bottom and like, we can work with these layers, as you suggested. So local, regional, more metal level. And so where should I put what? So farmers are on the local level. Right?.

P6 [00:24:58] Yeah.

I [00:24:58] Um. Okay. So I put farmers on the local level.

P6 [00:25:03] Um.

I [00:25:05] And where do I put the people and the public knowledge?

P6 [00:25:11] Um. Um, memento. Mm hmm.

P6 [00:25:21] If you put it like this. Also, I also see a different kind of system that's strategic, tactical and operational. And the farmers are operational.

P6 [00:25:33] Yeah. Oh, yeah. That is a good one.

I [00:25:39] Okay. So. I put this more in the middle. And what about research and knowledge dissemination?

P5 [00:25:56] Isn't that not strategic.

P6 [00:26:00] I think so, yeah.

I [00:26:01] So I put it up there. What? That's true.

P6 [00:26:07] But on the other hand, like I think research is even more tactic, I think because like, I have to be like a question pops from strategic level and then the researchers are going to invest on the specific project.

P5 [00:26:26] Yeah. Yeah, tactic.

I [00:26:41] Okay. Okay. I tried to. So you said this is more tactic?

P6 [00:27:02] So the top players are strategic. So that is governments and the top of companies and that kind of stuff. And then tactic is more the layer in between operational and strategic.

I [00:27:21] Okay. Okay. Nice. Um. So regarding the conditions, if we keep this structure now, do you think there's anything missing? So are there any elements that are not captured yet that are really needed, so that the transition can happen. Always keeping in mind that we're looking at information feedbacks and raising awareness and and so let's not try to get too much to other areas. But regarding this topic, are there any elements that are missing?

P6 [00:28:01] I would say regulation and laws in the strategic level, because that's also what law being is about for me. To change rules or to find new rules. I'm not sure if it's in that cycle, but it's one thing I didn't see.

I [00:28:25] And could you suggest how it is kind of related to the other, so are there any links to the other elements?

P6 [00:28:36] Most definitely.

I [00:28:39] Can you?

P6 [00:28:41] I open translate as sometimes I'm messing up my words in. So, for example, we in the Netherlands, we have this nitrogen how do you say it cause or whatever it's blocking every movement into the Netherlands right now for building, for farming, for everything, everything is stuck with that. So that's a regulation, a regulation problem, but it also can relate to things you have to do operational or solutions or if we do operational. I would say, but I don't know how Gabriela feels about that.

P5 [00:29:29] Yeah. No, definitely.

I [00:29:35] So if I understand you correctly, in the end, regulation is kind of influencing everything. So maybe I'm just connected to that.

P6 [00:29:47] To all the layers yeah.

I [00:29:48] And also to maybe farmer's knowledge in the end.

P6 [00:29:56] Yeah, but also you said in your description of what regenerative agriculture is. That it not only enhances environmentally, but also social and economic dimensions. So it's also about regulations and fair pricing. And those kind of forces that I saw on the left, those are regulated in a way.

I [00:30:20] Mm hmm.

I [00:30:23] And I put a plus or minus, put a plus or minus, because it depends on the regulation, if it's enhanced or decreased. Okay.

P5 [00:30:33] Yes. Yeah.

I [00:30:34] And what I would suggest now is and I liked also the idea of prioritising. So I mean we have a lot of interventions now. And perhaps it's a good thing to prioritise maybe on five interventions and look more deeply to them because otherwise I think we won't have enough time to think about everything. So what do you think are the most important interventions here or ideas that are not captured? From what you experienced in your work or from what you learned.

P5 [00:31:17] Yeah. If I look at the. What is it? Five. Promotion an healthy lifestyle, media use, information campaign, platforms for pioneers. Samples. Example models for regenerative agriculture. Yeah. Yeah, I can see they are all related in a quite, they are quite similar. Oh, I understand that you put them together on that first line uh huh. And then would you like us to chose like one of them as the most important one or would you.

I [00:32:18] I mean the layers are actually not really on purpose. That was more like trying to make it together to that you can read everything at the same time. But I think I see what you mean. So perhaps like I mean.

P5 [00:32:33] Yeah, they're quite similar some like information campaign.

I [00:32:37] I mean, I could just group them together, perhaps. I don't know. Platforms for pioneers and example models. For me, it's something else. Actually. For me, I see more like farmers making an example for others.

P5 [00:32:50] The example models is maybe a bit more education. Mm hmm. Yeah.

I [00:32:57] So I would maybe put them together. And maybe these three.

P5 [00:33:05] And this is more about campaigning and how you put it in the media and promote this.

P6 [00:33:14] Maybe it's not even promoting an healthy lifestyle, but more promoting healthy products, or not, it's not even a product. It's more like the way it's been farmed. That has to be promoted.

P5 [00:33:30] Promoting awareness of.

P6 [00:33:39] Also now like I am thinking if they just do normal milk or whatever I'm not sure. But that's also like a good diet and it's not about that's the way it has been farmed, I think.

I [00:33:51] Okay. I'm gonna change it. And so that's also nice. So we have these groups that I think is helpful. Can we find other groups?

P6 [00:34:05] Yeah, I don't know.

I [00:34:09] I mean, new narrative and new image. I think it's also similar.

P5 [00:34:13] Yeah.

P6 [00:34:16] Connecting farmers and society/community that can be the goal of platforms maybe? Or is that more what you mean, like an awareness for the customer?

I [00:34:27] MM Yeah. So I think what might be meant by this element is that if you kind of create more understanding of how farming works, so really make people understand where the product in the supermarket comes from. So understanding

P6 [00:34:44] Then that would be related to the post it about transparency and clarity about agricultural products.

I [00:34:54] I mean, that's also similar, I guess. And labels also belong to that, right?

P6 [00:35:06] What do you mean by labels?

I [00:35:08] I mean, I think there was an idea to introduce like a regenerative label, like a bio, organic, label. Just for a regenerative products.

P6 [00:35:19] Yeah. Like a proof for products. Those kind of things.

P5 [00:35:23] Yeah.

P6 [00:35:25] But then for real?

P5 [00:35:29] Yeah.

I [00:35:31] Okay. I mean, an experimental outside space, on-site demonstrations might also kind of belong together. Perhaps. What do you think?

P5 [00:35:41] Experimental outside spaces and on-site demonstrations. Yeah. Yeah.

I [00:35:54] Okay.

P5 [00:35:56] Maybe influencers is also media related. Mm hmm. Mm hmm. Yeah. Yeah.

I [00:36:05] So promoting. And. I mean, the other name of agriculture kind of also fits together with the new narrative right?

P5 [00:36:22] Yeah.

I [00:36:25] Okay. Nice. That is good. Now it would be great if we could connect these groups to the elements that we have on the, in the conditions area.

P5 [00:36:38] Yeah.

I [00:36:39] Do you have any suggestions how to do that?

P6 [00:36:59] I think the influencers group can be on the tactic level. Because that's about like people recognising values for nature. So these are people that relate to these kind of topics and want to contribute. Well. Platform is more in the operational, I think. Yeah. I think between maybe.

I [00:37:45] So do you think that why do you think it's in between?

P6 [00:37:50] Because it has to be bottom-up. But it has to also relate. It has to be done on a tactical level, I think.

I [00:38:04] Mm hmm.

P6 [00:38:05] So someone has to combine all those things that come from the operations, so to say.

I [00:38:10] Mm hmm. Mm hmm.

P6 [00:38:14] Several examples. And make a model for it. Yeah. But you need it in a co-working relation.

I [00:38:27] So when I understand you correctly, we kind of need farmers that recognise the value for regenerative agriculture to create these platforms. Right. Because otherwise we won't have them.

I [00:38:47] Okay. But we also need regulations. Or what you mean. What else do we need from the tactic or strategic level?

P6 [00:38:59] No, I think it has to relate to public recognising values for nature.

I [00:39:08] Mm hmm. Okay.

P6 [00:39:10] Because that's where you test the models on. If you have those values, you can test in the model if they contribute or not.

I [00:39:18] Mm hmm. Okay. Like this, right?

P6 [00:39:44] Mm hmm.

I [00:39:44] And somehow. I'm sorry.

P5 [00:39:48] Yeah. No, no, no. I was just checking. Yeah. So, like some.

I [00:39:58] Yeah, just interrupt me if anything is missing or wrong.

P5 [00:40:02] Yeah.

I [00:40:03] Um, I just had the idea. I don't know what you think about that. I mean, if we have platforms for pioneers, we were probably the most farmers with knowledge and awareness, right? So I mean the platform are for increasing the awareness of the farmers. Does it makes sense? I don't know what's what connect or what the platform is for otherwise.

P5 [00:40:28] Yes. That's a good one, actually. Yeah. It would make that we will have hopefully more farmers that will start with farmers, with knowledge and awareness of regenerative agriculture. Yeah, of course. That can be a plus. Yes. Yes.

I [00:40:49] Great. Okay. So we have. Um. Yeah, the other groups. Could you somehow also put them into the diagram?

P5 [00:41:10] Yes, I think that labels and true pricing also has to do with regulation. Yeah. Mm hmm. Yeah.

P6 [00:41:24] The only thing is that a regulation will not connect. I think farmers and society. I'm not sure. Otherwise there would have done already.

I [00:41:42] I see. So we have to kind of. And do you. Want to go. Back? Okay. Depends. Probably so regulations, we would need regulations for that. And enhance this transparency, Right?

P6 [00:42:12] So yeah, exactly. Yeah.

I [00:42:16] Um, okay. So we have like the connection left, the experimental outside spaces, which could also be related perhaps.

P6 [00:42:30] Yeah. It can also be connected to research on regenerative agriculture.

I [00:42:37] Which one?

P6 [00:42:40] It's in the top blue in the middle. Mm hmm. And it can be related to experimental outside spaces.

I [00:42:49] Mm hmm. And in which way so do you think research could enhance experimental outside spaces?

P6 [00:42:59] If land is available for, for studies, or for an experiment it can be related to a research program that will be funds for those long term investments. That's sort of how I see it. And that's what we do with our projects, for example, is we have a new building model or a new way of living together, we're gonna test it first from a research program and then in the end we can blow it out and it can be in the markets as well, but you have to test it first.

I [00:43:40] Mm hmm.

P6 [00:43:44] And that's a different thing than on-site demonstrations. Yeah.

I [00:43:48] Yeah. I leave it together for now.

P6 [00:43:51] And they're on the dilemma, right?

I [00:43:55] Sorry I didn't get that.

P6 [00:43:58] You understand the dilemma because there are not related in this cross link.

P6 [00:44:03] Yeah. Yeah.

P6 [00:44:04] And I mean, I also record this, so I will try to make it a bit more clearer after our interview. And so you said.

P5 [00:44:12] Now it's like a spider web.

I [00:44:15] Yeah, it always gets messy. I didn't find a better solution for that so far. So. And I just tried to add what you said, P6. With the research funding and. Yeah. Mm hmm. Nice. That's actually cool. Okay. Um. So it would be really cool if we could connect these two as well. And the new narrative. Um.

P5 [00:44:51] I know now. Yeah.

P6 [00:44:56] Does it also has to come from the labels. Is it same or different?

I [00:45:02] I mean, I could imagine.

P6 [00:45:04] I'm not sure.

I [00:45:05] If we have a new narrative. It kind would influence the labels? Definitely. If I like because if we have a new narrative, like the label would represent the new narrative in a way. Would be my interpretation of that. But I don't know what you think.

P5 [00:45:46] So again, with a new narrative we would have. What was your statement?

I [00:45:54] So my my, just my thought was that, if we would have a new narrative, the label would capture this. I mean, if the label, if we have a label, it would capture the new narrative and the question is if we need a new narrative to have labels. Or if. That's just my connection there. But maybe it's I don't know.

P5 [00:46:26] Yeah. So it has to do a little bit with regulations, so with.

P6 [00:46:31] Yeah. I can tell, so it has to come, it has to come from bottom down.

P5 [00:46:38] Yeah. Yeah.

I [00:46:41] Bottom down. So you mean it has to come from the farmers?

P6 [00:46:46] Yeah. Yeah. Or the people that are involved in the regulation of that agriculture, as a way.

I [00:46:57] So we kind of maybe put it here and.

P6 [00:47:03] Farmers recognize values and the black post it. You can link it to that and then it can be linked to. regulations?

I [00:47:19] And how would you think like regulation influence also influence the new image? Or is the new image influencing the regulations? What is the direction?

P6 [00:47:32] Relation? I think regulation will help to create a new image of regenerative agriculture. If the government sees this as positive and label it that way or put rules to that. Then?

P5 [00:48:03] Mm hmm.

I [00:48:04] So in the end also, kind of the label transparency thing would help. Yeah.

P5 [00:48:12] Okay. Yeah.

I [00:48:21] Okay. We still have left these connections/collaboration post-its.

P6 [00:48:33] Where is the platform? I would say that also the platform pioneers is a good way for collaborations. Mm hmm. It's what I was saying. Although the connecting farmers.

P5 [00:48:49] Yeah.

P6 [00:48:51] It's not only for pioneers, but it's also for exchange experiences and improve the model in a way.

I [00:49:09] Okay. And then this will also help to to get more farmers involved. Right. So I feedback it here.

P6 [00:49:21] When we're talking about lobbying. I know there's a European law that supports starting farmers to get more young people into farming because, yeah, someone has to produce the food for the future. So that can be related from an agricultural point of view, then it also can be regulated in a way.

I [00:49:52] So I would put lobbying to enhancing Okay. Nice. Um so these green post-its.

P5 [00:50:14] Yeah, there is still the connecting farmers and society/community. Yeah.

I [00:50:19] Yeah.

P5 [00:50:28] I think that's at the tactic.

P6 [00:50:37] To the public knowledge awareness post-it.

P5 [00:50:43] Yeah, exactly. Yeah.

I [00:50:53] And how. How this connection could be established. Do you have any ideas, how farmers and society could be more connected?

P6 [00:51:09] How can you repeat the question again?

I [00:51:12] So what? Do you have any idea how this connection between farmers and society could be established?

P5 [00:51:22] Uh huh. I just have like, uh, you have these organisations in the Netherlands carrying farmers and they organise, uh, open days. That's the audience. People who are not farmers can visit the farm and can see how it's. Oh, uh, yeah. What? What, what is their occupation? What is the daily? Yeah, it's I think it's to make it feasible and to have people who are not in these fields. Um.

Mhm. To involve them is, is about organising open days or organising meetups and really have meet and feel the farm and be there to be going around. Mm hmm. Yeah.

I [00:52:37] And I mean, I just saw is this somehow related to the experimental outside space as well?

P5 [00:52:47] Yeah.

I [00:52:49] So and just like because we need this it is on site demonstrations perhaps. Kind of.

P5 [00:52:58] Yes.

I [00:53:00] Okay? Yeah, I guess so.

P5 [00:53:02] There's a license? Yeah. Yeah.

I [00:53:05] Sorry for, like the messiness now.

P5 [00:53:08] Oh, yeah. I need more glasses.

P6 [00:53:13] Mm hmm. I also zoomed it in.

I [00:53:18] Yeah. So let me know. Otherwise, I try to. Okay. Um. Yeah, Because, um, besides interventions, I mean, we also have barriers, so that's why I had, like, put these two green post-its. So I. It's a moment we've talked a lot about what interventions can do, so what could be done. But there are also things that kind of hinder the transition to happen. And from the workshops last year, these two post-its were mentioned. So lobbying against regenerative agriculture and dominance of conventional agriculture institutions. Um do you think they have any relevance in this kind of mess that we already created? Or can you think of other barriers that are existing?

P6 [00:54:23] Yeah. They are right. That's the question you posed first. But I think, yeah, for sure you missed something. And these are not only the topics. I think through pricing while the prize now I would say for our regular food is not transparent and is not. It's actually too cheap, at least in the Netherlands. Mm hmm. That's why people are not switching to biological food or regenerative food. Because there's also a lobby that's been having a lot of extra funds going into the prize.

I [00:55:26] So kind of the lobby for against regenerative agriculture decreases. So I put a minus actually. the price for regular food. That's what you meant.

P6 [00:55:39] Yeah.

I [00:55:39] And how is this related to our map? So is it. That the reason why people don't recognise value for nature and food. Or people. So the awareness is not rising, so. Or is it something else?

P6 [00:56:01] Maybe it's also a cultural thing, I think.

I [00:56:05] Okay.

P6 [00:56:06] It is about values, but also cultural values because it's something new you have to protect. We know that kind of change is always hard.

I [00:56:22] Okay. So I'll add this link.

P6 [00:56:32] And also the link that true pricing can have a negative effect regarding to the price of regular food. Mm hmm. That's quite interesting cause today or yesterday there was the overtime. It's like one of the biggest supermarkets in the Netherlands is selling a coffee for true price and it's going quite far now, so people are getting more aware of what true pricing means because they don't have. It's also that culture is not there yet. There's stuff out there a lot, and that in your face. I would say.

I [00:57:21] I just put it like this and. And I would connect it. How would you connect? Directly to the price or to the lobbying.

P6 [00:57:42] Maybe even dominance of conventional agricultural institutions. Well, it's actually a negative thing.

I [00:58:06] Negative. Okay.

P6 [00:58:07] Oh, yeah. All right. I'm sorry. No.

I [00:58:09] No, I understand. It's a little bit. Like it's a negative post-it, but a positive relationship. Yeah. Mm hmm.

P6 [00:58:18] Yeah.

I [00:58:19] And how would you connect the culture of not wanting to change and the dominance of conventional institutions to the web?

P6 [00:58:32] People recognising the values for nature, agriculture, and food.

I [00:58:43] So this is kind of. A now. This is from farmers, right?

P6 [00:58:54] Oh, yeah. In that way, the Netherlands is a quite interesting case to look at right now, because this political party that just won the elections right now.

I [00:59:12] Okay. And they don't want changes.

P6 [00:59:16] No, they want conventional agriculture.

I [00:59:20] O wow ok.

P6 [00:59:25] Even the nitrogen nitrogen crisis is off for debate again.

I [00:59:30] Oh, wow. So really regulation and government seems to be super important aspect from what I can read from there ok.

P6 [00:59:46] I think it also depends on which country you are. I think Gabriela knows more about that, but it's really changing over land. In the Netherlands it's so dense, it's so compact. So you have to regulate everything. But maybe in Portugal or Spain it's different.

I [01:00:08] Interesting.

P5 [01:00:10] Yeah.

P6 [01:00:11] That's what I mean with culture.

I [01:00:14] Mm hmm. Okay. I mean, I will have a look at the time. Okay. So, I mean, we already I think did great work. Thank you very much. And now maybe. Hey. Yeah, I think I would give you maybe a try to zoom in as much as possible, and you can just have another calm look at it and see if you want to add anything or change anything. And perhaps we didn't touch the consequences yet. For me, they're not as important as the condition and interventions, so that's fine. But I mean, if you just look at it and if you can think of any consequences. So what happens if these condition would be fulfilled? How would the transition look like? I think that's kind of the question and we could add it, but no pressure. I mean, I think it was already quite, quite a work here. I'm going to try to zoom in

as much as possible. And maybe like this. And you let me know if I should kind of shift somewhere and. Yeah.

P6 [01:01:29] Try to make it simple. That's the only thing I would say.

P5 [01:01:34] Yeah.

P6 [01:01:36] Very simple. Because otherwise it's such a broad subject. It could go wild if you would like. This theme alone is already a research study in itself.

I [01:01:48] Yeah, that's true. That's true. Yeah. I mean, I realise that also with regard to all the other STEs, I mean it's huge, this topic and focusing on the different areas, it's already tried to kind of make it a little bit categorised and focussed in a way. But yeah, in each category you can jump out of it and go into the other areas and. Yeah, huge topic.

P6 [01:02:15] Maybe the SDGs can help you with categorise them a bit more.

I [01:02:20] So what?

P6 [01:02:20] Sustainable development goals?

I [01:02:23] Yeah.

P6 [01:02:24] Those are like there are people, but also economics. Also socials. Soils. For me that helps a lot to also take a few.

I [01:02:37] Yeah, yeah, yeah.

P6 [01:02:39] I yeah, I wish we can do them all, but that's in these days is not possible yet. I hope to visit this summer, I hope to visit a project in Norway or something. And that's the first project that has all the SDGs in it. And I really am curious how is did this.

P5 [01:02:59] Oh yeah. How nice. Which was, which was.

P6 [01:03:03] Oh, I will text you again.

P5 [01:03:05] Yeah, I read them. Nice.

I [01:03:11] Okay. But are there any like is there anything what is really super important regarding information dissemination, which is not to captured. I think that's maybe the last question. So is there really anything you can think of which is not in this map yet? Which is really important, which I should at somehow one of the maps.

P6 [01:03:35] Yeah. The only thing I think of again regarding to the the definition you gave on regenerative agriculture is the environmental profits. That's something we didn't discuss before. It's for the lobbying, for a research program for any awareness it's really important to show a difference because that's what I think the biggest of a farm really shows the benefits for the environment. Also show them what the benefit is because people can't really see beyond their own perspective. So you have to show them the promised land so to say.

P5 [01:04:28] Yeah. And. Oh, yeah, that's a good one. And it's also a challenging one because with regenerative agriculture, it takes years and years. Um, I'm thinking now of this project in Spain where they started eight years ago. And yeah, it's, uh, huge. It's 1100, 11,000 square feet meter. Oh, wow. How much is that? Anyway, It's very big piece of land and they are almost completely regenerative. Yeah, it's a long process of years and years. If you want to show it, you have to fast forward movie like. But of course, with my biggest little farm, it's also something shot in many years right. And it's a challenging one, but it's good. It's also a part of making things feasible is capturing, I don't know. For example, there's somebody who's thinking drone images of fruit forests and you see it, every years you see the change and that's that's something that makes it really visible, because then you can see real difference in what it's doing.

I [01:06:17] So it's somehow also related to information campaigns in the end. I would say so taking pictures and like publishing them and writing them out.

P5 [01:06:28] Yeah.

I [01:06:30] Okay. And I'm thinking in parallel how to connect this and have the feeling it's connected to everything now. And yeah.

P5 [01:06:40] And so it's visualisation and long and longer term projects and you could connect it to tactic.

I [01:06:58] It's kind of related to that, but I think it's also related to on-site demonstrations, like on the experimental sets basis in a way where you could show it. I don't know if it's possible.

P5 [01:07:08] Right. Yeah. Yeah

I [01:07:12] Um maybe I would just draw connections to remember myself and see later how I will put this together. Okay. Nice. Thank you. Okay, so it's almost 5:30. I don't know when you have to leave.

P6 [01:07:39] Yeah in a bit.

I [01:07:39] Okay. Um, okay. So any last comments before you have to go?

P6 [01:07:53] That's my dog answering. Sorry. You know. It's such a broad topic, so I think if you can just leave it to these kind of topics and just make them really simple and right. It's already an accomplishment I would say.

I [01:08:10] So yeah, because my question would be I would try to clean this up and make it a little bit, make it look nicer. And if it would be okay for you, I would like to send it to you again and just to have you a look and give me last feedback on. Okay, if you think that the connections are fine, that the elements are important and that would be great if it's okay for you.

P6 [01:08:35] Yeah, for me that would be actually great because it's it's also inspiring. It also gives me ideas for my pioneers platform. So I think it's very, very interesting and it would be great to have it a bit more organised and structured.

I [01:08:56] I will try to do that. Okay. And, you know, so my last question would be if you have any feedback for me, how I could organise interviews and do the interviews, because I mean, you are actually my first interview, now. And so if you have any nice feedback for me, it would be super helpful for the for the other interviews. And if I could yes, I could do anything. Just let me know.

P5 [01:09:27] Yeah. I think you have a great starting point now when you have the structure a bit more organised. Uh. But maybe if it's if you have a especially more organised, it's also easier maybe to go further into it and to talk about. Uh huh. So you the how and how and why and the actual steps that could be taken. Mm hmm. Accomplish something. Yeah. Yeah.

I [01:10:09] Yeah. I actually like that said it. It's helpful to kind of have an organisation in the post-its, and to prioritise. I think I would keep that in mind for the other interviews. Well, a little bit to, um, yeah to get into the different post-its. I think it was a good feedback. Thank you.

P6 [01:10:31] Yeah. I don't know any other arguments for that. I wish you good luck.

I [01:10:39] Yeah, thank you very much. Okay, so you don't have anything else. Thank you very much for your time. And yeah let me know if you have questions. I will now try to clean that up as soon as possible, but I think it would take a few weeks.

P6 [01:11:02] Take your time.

I [01:11:02] I will go back to or come back to you?

P6 [01:11:06] Yeah.

P5 [01:11:06] So nice.

I [01:11:07] So have a nice evening.

P6 [01:11:08] Thank you.

I [01:11:09] Thank you very much.

P6 [01:11:12] Thank you. Bye bye.

P5 [01:11:13] Bye. Bye bye. Thanks.